

Delphi consensus study – Round 3

We are very grateful to the 19 experts who participated to the two first rounds and welcome you to this important third round. During this round, you are to validate the theoretical framework we have agreed on for mobility management during transport transition (Mobility Management Programs). We will also share some relevant conceptual contradictions you revealed during Round 2 and have you validate our suggested resolutions.

This round includes 10 questions. They are organized in 5 sections. Each section ends with the list of detailed responses we received during the second round. Completing the form requires approximatively 15-20 minutes.

Comments:

Some participants had difficulties completing the questionnaire using Windows Explorer (e.i. not able to continue to next section). Their problem was solved by changing browser and using Chrome.

The term "client" can be interchanged with the term "patient". When caregivers are involved, the term "clients" refers to the person with health deficits and the caregiver.

* Required

1. Please provide your StudyID : *

.....

Treatment framework for mobility management during transport transition

Graphical representation

The full image can be accessed at the following link: <http://postimg.org/image/fo5lb5mux/>
(click on "Full size" at the bottom of the page to have an optimal definition on your screen)

Figure 1: Treatment framework for Mobility Management Programs

Stages of progress defined for Mobility Management Programs

Stage 1 - "Consideration"

This stage sees clients being confronted by age related changes and the difficulties this might lead to. Depending on the severity of cognitive impairment, caregivers can be integrated at this stage of the procedure. Ideally, clients enter the program early enough to have a reassuring timeframe during which changes can be brought progressively before driving cessation occurs. During this stage, clients are brought to focus on their strengths instead of their difficulties. They are engaged to discuss about potential future scenario of failing health and impact on driving abilities. They can also be confronted to the difficulties they experience whilst driving. With a better understanding of the problem, the decision to cease driving shifts from an imposed external decision to a personal decision motivated by their sense of self-responsibility. Clients are confronted to positive experiences, such as the advantages in driving cessation and witnesses from peers. They are brought to understand and manage normal grieving process positively, and change their emotional attachment to driving from a right to a privilege. They are also brought to consider the advantage of being able to successfully use alternative mode of transport, to realize it will enable them to engage out-of-home activities and to believe in their capabilities. Thereby making the idea of change possible.

Stage 2 - "Acceptance"

This phase has clients make the decision of transition their own. Clients are brought to accept their need for change. They can create their own narrative for their personal reasons for discontinuing driving and be emotionally and rationally convinced that such a change is necessary. They can be brought to try out alternative means of transport to experience their advantages. This stage ends once clients own the decision of transition and can create their own narrative of change in cultural adaptation. Clients who suffers from anosognosia and are unable to accept the situation (i.e. not to confuse with the denial phase of grief), are to move on to the next stage and negotiate solutions with caregiver. In the absence of a caregiver, this role should be taken by a person of the client's choice.

Stage 3 - "Action"

This phase has clients explore possible alternatives to choose those that are most adapted in maintaining meaningful occupations. Clients develop planning skills and learn to set goals. They discuss transport options with family, caregivers or community support. Clients are brought to adjust performance patterns of valued occupations to meet the availability of alternative transportation. They are provided with support in developing a feasible plan for how they will implement these changes, and in problem-solving unforeseen circumstances. They are to improve their capacity for change and movement in transport. This involves trying out different ways and means of transport in a try and error approach. This stage ends once clients have negotiated a

personal plan for alternative mobility options.

Stage 4 - "Autonomy"

This phase has clients take confidence in their ability to implement and adapt chosen changes in behaviour. This longer phase consists of a follow-up period (maximum 6 months) during which solutions are adjusted and clients learn to perceive instability as an ongoing challenge. There is therefore a progressive decrease in the support provided by the occupational therapist as clients recover their autonomy in choosing appropriate strategies. Self-monitoring is used to have clients implement their plan efficiently (i.e. maintain participation in valued community activities, as good as before occupational balance and well-being). This stage ends once clients are able to manage their mobility without overloading the caregiver. This endpoint might never be achieved and could require monitoring from the GP to provide further support when needed.

2. How relevant do you find the treatment framework for answering client's needs independently of available resources ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

3. How relevant do you find working with transtheoretical stages (Stages 1-4) when addressing transport transition ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

4. How relevant do you find to plan changes early in health decline so to anticipate difficulties ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

5. How relevant do you find the implication of caregivers for Mobility Management Programs ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

6. How relevant do you find the expected long-term outcomes (i.e. long term goals in previous version) ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

7. Do you have any further critics or comments on the proposed treatment framework for managing mobility during transport transition ?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Your previous comments during Round 2 (optional reading)

Question Round 2: Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition and representation of "treatment goals"?

A. Timeframe

MOBILE6893 : As I see clients only on the day of the assessment, and provide them with the information about their driving status, there is no opportunity to implement any of these goals in other than an arbitrary manner. The driving process is arranged through private practice, and clients pay per contact. There is no scheduled follow up for these goals to be implemented. If I was working with a client long term, rather than seeing them only of the day of the driving test, I would use this framework very well. In the absence of any support staff after the test, the client would need to do this themselves, or with minimal input from me on the phone suggesting resources and options. Even with a support person, the likelihood of regaining autonomy is very small in a rural area due to lack of tranport alternatives. I know I keep making these points, but that is my reality and that of my clients.

MOBILE6146 : a timeframe of 6 months may not be realistic for some individuals as their cognitive and mental status may frustrate.

MOBILE6211 : I think that this makes the transition seem too uniform and predictable. My experience is that the transition is a bit of a moving target - and the short term goals vary widely and occur and recur - while the "final goals" are not really achieved fully as further reasons for adaptation keep occurring. I think it is more meaningful to develop an approach that meets people where they are at and sets goals with them according.

MOBILE7932 : I'm still not sure that the person has to accept they have to retire from driving, or have it be their own decision in order to move on/regain community mobility.

B. Caregiver :

MOBILE3940 : Difficult to recognise capability with cognitive impairment

MOBILE3618 : 'Own Decision' not always possible when lack of insight due to cognitive change is an issue.

C. Final Goal Measurability

MOBILE3499 : How can you validate final goals? How can these be monitored ?

MOBILE7932 : There is also no mention of 'community mobility' (out of home activity levels) in the figure

MOBILE8255 : I would also comment that I do not perceive social engagements as separate to maintaining meaningful occupations - they would be one of the occupations that are maintained.

D. Continuous Goal

MOBILE8255 : People also need to learn how to use and become confident in using alternative transport options. This would be seen as an important facilitator and therefore part of the continuous goals.

MOBILE8741 : There is an important problem in the proposed model, due to assumptions that treatment goals can be set independently of the client. This is a false assumption. Either the model NEEDS to include goal negotiation with the "client system" or change the idea that you are setting goals. Could it be outcomes or important aspects, or really a model of things that might be addressed in this situation. Please change this !

E. Short Term

MOBILE3032 : make decision - can start in the second box of short term goals.

F. Consistency Titles

MOBILE3618 : I am assuming that Final Goals is the same as Long Term Goals.

Question : Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition of "Stage1" ?

A. Transtheoretical Model Defied / Timeframe

MOBILE6211 : I also think for many people they need to actually try out and be able to successful use alternatives before they come to any feelings of acceptance. For most this doesn't all happen before any action.

MOBILE3940 : Extremely relevant however, not so easily achieved.

MOBILE6146 : Although the principles seem logical, many individuals with depressive symptoms and memory difficulties may take much longer time to understand the extent of their driving problem.

MOBILE2503 : This can begin well before driver cessation is required. We often plan to retire from work, downsize living situations however we rarely appreciate that we will need to retire from driving at some point. There doesn't necessarily need to be a diagnosis to begin this process and it should be initiated very early on.

MOBILE7932 : I think its important to focus on clients strengths at this stage. They are made 'aware' that driving is not an option, but may not 'accept' it per se. Again, they may never see the advantages of giving up driving, rather they may realize alternatives are available that can enable them to engage in out-of-home activities. also do not understand that they are 'confronted' by positive experiences. What does this mean? That their strengths are explored? What does an imposed external constraint to self-responsibility mean? They know there is a change that is impact their medical fitness to drive. As such, they consider mobility alternatives by exploring their own strengths and resources that are available in their community (inc. social networks). I would keep the explication more succinct.

B. Context

MOBILE3032 : This will happen if client is willing to be engaged. Ideally this stage should start early at Memory Clinic when patient is diagnosed with MCI/early dementia.

MOBILE6893 : These matters ar often discussed with the client's doctor before they see me. While I may want to offer these supports, services and insights to the client, this does not happen. If they fail the test, they are usually angry and will not hear any of heh above information.

C. Terminology

MOBILE3032 : Reassurance should be given that at this early stage, there is a 'window' period for driving competently which will decline with progression of illness.

MOBILE3618 : I think it should also include 'clients being confronted by age related changes' not just a health condition.

D. Patient Centered

MOBILE6211 : I don't think this is clear - I don't think it is realistic or even optimal that people will see advantages. The wording also makes the retired drivers' roles very passive.

E. Caregiver

MOBILE3776 : Lack of insight due to cognitive issues will not make this a smooth process.

F. Emotional Attachment

MOBILE6893 : Occasionally, a small percentage of clients - usually female - will make the decision to surrender their licence. Rarely have I have that experience with most clients, and especially males over the age of 75 who view driving as a right, not a privilege, and a blow to their egos to lose it. Discussions about the effect on their health and safety and that of other community members, will help them.

G. Consistency with Goals

MOBILE8255 : This definition makes this endpoint clearer. However, I wonder if the final sentence and endpoint is appropriate. Is this about being ready to change? That is more than being aware of advantages.

H. Others

MOBILE8741 : Much better.

Question : Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition of "Stage2"?

A. Timeframe

MOBILE6146 : Similar to answer to 'consideration', some individuals may present a fragmented or distorted narrative which makes it difficult for them to accept driving cessation.

MOBILE4380 : I find your endpoint very relevant but I am usually working with the clients who are unable to reach this stage themselves and the decision has been forced on them by an outside source which leads to the driving assessment.

MOBILE3618 : Completely relevant when a client doesn't have insight issues.

MOBILE3940 : In my 24 years of practising driver assessment and rehabilitation there have been very few drivers who are able to make this decision independently.

MOBILE6893 : Refer to previous comments about the rarity of people making this decision on their own.

MOBILE3776 : Clients rarely make this decision on their own. Even after accidents.

B. Caregiver

MOBILE7564 : Sometimes the client isn't totally accepting of the need to stop driving but trusts the perspective of a 'trusted' family member - one gentleman didn't agree that his skills had declined but trusted his wife of 50+ years when she said he was different.

MOBILE3032 : Family members play a critical role to persuade the client to make the decision to stop voluntarily. However, those who are fiercely independent may ignore the considerations of the family or lack the positive support to do the right thing.

C. Move forward even if endpoint not achieved

MOBILE6211 : I don't think this is a single set point. I think acceptance and ownership will fluctuate over time and with further life changes. I don't think endpoints really work as a concept here.

MOBILE7932 : Again, I'm not sure convincing someone that they should accept that driving is no longer an option is important and having them say 'okay' I can't drive. Acceptance would of course be optimal, but I know people who have been told they will never walk again, and I'm not there to take away their dream, rather to help them explore alternatives that can keep them healthy and mobile in their community in the meantime.

D. Context (Early management)

MOBILE3499 : I think clients will find this difficult and there might be some conflict. With all of these stages what sorts of information will be used?

MOBILE6893 : Once again, this is relevant to the client, but not applicable in a private practice setting. I can provide follow up referrals for the client to consider, but there is no funding for me to walk the journey with them while these adjustments are being made.

E. Clarify

MOBILE8741 : It might need more description of the process that clients might take, acceptance has such a wide understanding. It might be useful to have more examples of what the clients might

show as behaviours in this phase. I like the owned narratives, as something that can be observed in this stage. I think this would need more input from more people than 8925.

Question : Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided definition of "Stage3"?

Caregiver

MOBILE3032 : Family caregiver/s are usually involve in this as well esp for drivers progressing to moderate dementia/with issues in executive functioning.

MOBILE3499 : How do you take into account contextual factors such as access to family or social support ?

MOBILE3776 : Not possible with dementia.

MOBILE4380 : Once again I find that most clients and families will work through this stage with an outside source or on their own. The client is usually referred to me as they are unable to come to this endpoint on there own. Unfortunately, this endpoint is often decided for the client through the means of a driving assessment an consequently the client does not reach this endpoint but the families do.

MOBILE6146 : Some individuals will not be able to make decisions and choose their own alternative transport options without close family and friends. Family may also need support and advice in the decision-making process.

MOBILE7564 : [...] In one couple - the adjustment was as much the wife who moved from the passenger seat back to driver's seat. As she was the primary 'alternative' for her husband who stopped driving, she had to engage in more planning to meet both their transportation needs. The involvement of family in this step is critical to success. The variety of options and match of options to occupation typically requires assistance of family.

B. Available resources for alternative transport

MOBILE3940 : This stage would be much more successful I F Drives actually had suitable alternatives to driving especially for spur of the moment needs/wants.

MOBILE6893 : I encourgae clients to discuss alternatives, but few realistic ones available.

MOBILE7564 : Some clients can only set the plans with assistance of others due to cognitive decline. Another issue I've encountered is the need to adjust performance patterns of valued occupations to meet the availability of alternative transportation. [...]

C. Transtheoretical theory

MOBILE6211 : Again, I don't see this as a linear process. Some people can't reach the earlier "endpoints" without having trialled some alternatives. Some planning works well while people are in good health or while spouse is living but falls apart later.. i think this is a bit oversimplified. i think theoretical planning of transport use is not at all helpful.

MOBILE8255 : This needs to include more than just developing a plan. People need to trial and decide on which option is best for them. This practical aspect needs to be much more explicit.

MOBILE8741 : I think this phase needs to include trying out different ways and means of transport, the doing of occupations is also absent. This should include a change in occupations linked with the try and error of using varied transportation options. [...]

D. Wording

MOBILE7932 : I'm not sure the client 'sets' the feasible plan per se, rather the client 'has' a plan for alternative mobility options (vs. adapted alternative solutions). determined. This phase is well articulated and explained. I think its important to keep the mobility word in these respective steps.

MOBILE8741 : [...] I don't think the endpoint 3 is realistic, feasible plan isn't sufficient as an endpoint for this stage.

I would add to this phase more capacity for change and movement in transport. You need to take into account more individualised solutions and ways of doing things, also. Occupation-focused may be lost in this stage.

E. Support – follow-up

MOBILE6893 : If a client has family support, alternatives may be considered and implemented. If not, they may descend into depression or isolation. If they have a case manager, they may provide this role, but this clientele would represent about 5 % of my clients.

Question : Do you have any critics (positive or negative) or comments to add for the provided

definition of "Stage4"?

A. Wording

MOBILE2503 : Sometimes changes don't necessarily facilitate access to somewhere - may change place of activity etc. to better facilitate participation.

MOBILE6893 : Not sure who their facilitator could be in most circumstances.

MOBILE7564 : I wouldn't assume a 'decrease in assistance' as those with cognitive decline might need more assistance - unless you are considering the family who is assisting with the planning of alternatives becomes more skilled and knowledgeable.

MOBILE7932 : - Use the term client, as opposed to patient. - ...places they want (remove to). -why is there a time element? why 6 months? - i.e., not e.i.

MOBILE8741 : It is endpoint 4 here, not 3.

B. Autonomy

MOBILE6893 : I have no role as a facilitator. Unless they have excellent community and family support, it is unlikely that they will achieve this stage.

Once again, integration is essential to the client being able to adjust to their altered circumstances and the next phase of their life. They would have to accomplish this on their own or actively seek professional support to undertake this process. Not with me.

MOBILE7932 : Why self-manage? could it just be client is able to manage - some clients will always require help/assistance from others yet consider themselves 'independent, which is worth considering.

C. Change title (Integration) ?

MOBILE6211 : Really not sure of use of patients in a community context. Again, I think these stages and endpoints are problematic as they assume everyone has the same process and needs and that is not the case. I think it needs to be much more fluid and individualised. "Solutions" are not final meeting all the person's needs and it is not unusual for people to continue to need to change and adjust patterns with regular changes to year (weather/seasons) and with changes to their health and situation - I am not sure repetition is therefore a useful approach here.

MOBILE6146 : Not sure what 'integrate implemented changes in behaviour' means. Some individuals may not be able to 'self-manage their mobility without further help'.

D. Available resources

MOBILE3032 : Payment for professional OT services to do this is a barrier to clients in my culture. This phase is thus taken over by the family member generally. Self monitoring by the clients themselves may not happen due to the stage of the illness.

MOBILE3499 : There are significant resource costs implied by the model. Also, how do clients travel to and from the clinic.

E. Caregiver

MOBILE3776 : Follow-up is most important. It must include caregivers.

Expected possible changes of behaviour targeted in Mobility Management Programs

Domains of changes	Description	Subdomains : patient centred approach	Examples
A) Occupation	Maintain and prioritize meaningful activities and abandon those that are least important to guarantee occupational balance and well-being (person's choice and negotiation).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Modify occupational priorities ▪ Modify occupational roles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Relinquish voluntary work at library ▪ Take care of grandchildren at home ▪ Shop online
B) Social interactions	Restructure social engagement in community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accept help from others ▪ Use of technologies for communication ▪ Change context of interactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accept been driven by partner ▪ Using social media to communicate with grandchildren ▪ Organise art workshops at home instead of attending classes in town
C) Emotional attachments	Overcome the notion of loss and grief and reluctance to change.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recover feeling of safety ▪ Improve resilience ▪ Transfer emotional attachments ▪ Accept loss 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Having an available relative over the phone while waiting for the bus ▪ Discovering benefits of social interactions in public transport ▪ Read paper in car because likes the smell of the leather seats
D) Extrapersonal	Change the role of caregivers, relatives, friends and/or community support in supporting transport changes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Caregivers ▪ Community support ▪ Infrastructure (physical environment) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Providing support to caregiver to help manage mobility and prevent overload ▪ Coordinate community health services ▪ In case of snow, salt sidewalk to access to train station
E) Transport	Use alternative means of transport and include changes to occupational performance patterns.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use public transports ▪ Use transportation assistance ▪ Use individualized mean of locomotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Take the bus and train to visit gynaecologist ▪ Learn to use a gopher
F) Relocation	Modify destination for occupation or place of residency.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Modify destination for occupation ▪ Relocate occupation at home ▪ Modify place of residency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Change hairdresser ▪ Redesigning living room to welcome card players at home ▪ Move in secondary residency close to family
G) Cognitive process	Adjust memory, attention and decision processes. Learn how to manage within current capabilities		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Teach how to focus attention on a single task ▪ Adjusting ability to plan strategies for alternative transport options in case of bad weather

8. To what extent do you find this classification of behaviour change as relevant for addressing transport transition?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Irrelevant Completely relevant

9. Do you have any further critics or comments on the above table ?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Linking changes to stages

Figure 3

STAGES DOMAINS	Stage 1 Consideration	Stage 2 Acceptation	Stage 3 Action	Stage 4 Autonomy
Occupation				
Social interactions				
Emotional attachments				
Extrapersonal				
Transport				
Relocation				
Cognitive process				

Stages during which behavioural changes are expected to occur (n=15). Black boxes correspond to 100% of experts expecting change, white boxes to 0%

Description Figure 3

During Round 2, you were asked to identify the stage of mobility management during which you were expecting behaviour changes to occur. The figure above summarizes your answers by showing how many of you agreed. The lowest level of agreement was 40% (transport and social interaction at stage 1).

Overall, "emotional attachment" and "cognitive processes" are expected to change sooner than other domains whereas "relocation" and changes in "social interactions" are expected to change at a later stage. However, changes seem to be expected throughout the procedure of mobility management. These changes are therefore believed to change progressively respecting the transtheoretical model.

Example: Changes in opinions on the use of public transport can be initiated at the "consideration" stage (stage 1). Having a client try the alternative can bring them to change their level of acceptance for such an alternative mean of transport (stage 2). During stage 3, the client could learn to set goals and plan and organize their mobility using public transport when possible. During the final stage, the client would become able to face changes in timetables and restructure their use of public transports accordingly.

10. **Do you find relevant to consider changes as a continuous process taking place throughout the four stages of Mobility Management Programs ?**

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

Your previous comments during Round 2 (optional reading)

A) Occupation

MOBILE8741 : Change patient's choice into person's choice and negotiation, move out has to be seen as a last resort and only if the person so chooses.

In occupation, change should guarantee occupational balance and well-being

B) Social Interactions

MOBILE7932 : What about social network of individual? This also seems an important area to explore/ascertain with the client beyond simply social engagement per se.

C) Emotional attachments

MOBILE6893 : The inclusion of emotional components is important. There is a focus on support of children - many clients do not have them or have no meaningful relationship with them.

MOBILE3940 : Need to consider that extensive changes add another level of grief to an already stressful situation ie they lose their ability to drive and live in the family home

D) Extrapersonal : -

E) Transport

MOBILE7564 : also could include changes to occupational performance patterns once using alternative transportation.

MOBILE4380 : A lot of clients are dictated in their decision making by finances. I find that this area often needs to be addressed as they find alternate means of transport expensive and it is important to demonstrate what it costs them to own and run a car and then compare those expenses to what the cost of the alternative transport options are. Once this fear is laid to rest, they are then able to commence to move on.

F) Relocation

MOBILE7932 : Is it improving accessibility to what? or is it improving mobility?

MOBILE6211 : but relocation is an odd domain of change and not a necessary one (it is a change that occurs for some).

MOBILE8255 : It strikes me strange that relocation is a domain of change. This might be something that happens during the process of aiming to maintain occupations or due to transport, but not necessarily as a domain on its own.

G) Cognitive process

MOBILE8255 : I am unclear on the cognitive process. The aim is not to improve memory, attention, etc. that implies remediation of lost skills. However the examples are linked more to learning how to manage within current capabilities. There is a disconnect between these two.

MOBILE6893 : Cognitive processes - with a focus on improvement, consideration must also be given to the high incidence of ongoing decline rather than any possibility of improvement, and the

emotional and practical considerations of the client adjusting to the effects of the decline.

Global Comments :

MOBILE3032 : the stage of dementia will limit or exclude some of the targets in these domain of changes.

MOBILE7932 : I think it is critical to use Canadian Occupational Performance Measure (COPM) to explore/measure client satisfaction/performance with regard to his/her perspective too - their is no mention client (& caregiver; if appropriate).

MOBILE6211 : I don't understand this aspect - I don't know if the order is supposed to indicate importance or temporal aspects (...). I think it is hugely important to indicate that these changes be driven by retired/retiring driver and not the therapist. I can't follow how some of these link to what is coded under them in submitted responses (eg cognitive processes). I am not sure examples for occupational change capture that domain as I understand it.

Underlying theoretical models

Focus on a limited number of theoretical models

The treatment framework for Mobility Management Programs mainly relies on four underlying models: the Transtheoretical Model of Behaviour Change (Prochaska & DiClemente 1983), the health Action Process Approach (Schwarzer 2008), the Transactional Model (Cotchin & Dickie 2013), and the Client-Centeredness Goal Setting Approach (Doig et al. 2015).

11. To what extent do you find the limited choice to these four models as relevant ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Irrelevant	<input type="radio"/>	Completely relevant									

Difficulties and suggested solutions

During the second round, experts came up with challenging paradoxes that made clinical sense. We therefore took them into consideration when revising this version. Please read the following four apparent contradictions we had to face and let us know if you agree with the solutions we suggest.

1. Experts found a certain incompatibility between the use of the Transtheoretical model and their need for flexibility in moving to next stages without having achieved the set goals (Endpoints). Two arguments supported this flexibility: 1) clients could conceive changes and accept them but then change their mind later on, and 2) it can help experiencing a change to accept it. We have therefore added small pathways over the Endpoints to show that it is possible to move from one stage to another without necessarily having achieved the previous ones.

2. Optimisation of mobility management requires flexibility and important changes in habits and behaviour. In our framework, this is believed to improve mental well-being. However, changes can be an important source of stress in aged community dwellers (continuity theory of normal ageing). This would affect mental well-being negatively. Therefore, we suggest using a patient-centered goal setting approach that should limit risks linked to the process of change (grief, stress, and depression).

3. We have received many comments on the importance of having the client make choices and decisions (patient-centred approach). In the same time, we have received many comments from clinicians who rely on caregivers to take decisions due to the severity of the clients cognitive decline. We therefore suggest including caregivers in the process to help client negotiate solutions. To prevent conflicts between clients and their caregiver, we however consider that decisions can be taken by caregivers only if a psychogeriatric evaluation has shown the client to be unable to do so. This implies that negotiations must preserve the caregiver and measures must be taken not to shift the problem of loss of social engagement to the caregiver.

4. The expected domains of change identified by experts do not correspond to the domains of change described in the behaviour change technique taxonomy (behavioral determinants). For the purpose of solving this issue, the four members of the research team analyzing your answers are considering following a BCT training (<http://www.bct-taxonomy.com/>). This would then make it possible for them to classify your suggested techniques and examples into a standardized appellation. In Round 4, this will have us ask you to provide examples of behaviour change techniques you might use to enhance changes within each stage.

12. **Do you agree with our suggestions and if you do not, could you develop why and make further suggestions ?**

.....

Your previous comments during Round 2 (optional reading)

A. Update

MOBILE3499 : There are lots of models, but behaviour takes place in a context and social support needs to be taken into account.

MOBILE3776 : I have developed another model: Multifactor Older Driver with Dementia Evaluation Model (MODEM). Published in 2. Carr, D. & Hunt, L. (2016). Driving and transportation: Dementia as a model for evaluation, decision-making, and planning. In K.F. Barney & M.A. Perkinson (Eds.). Occupational therapy with aging adults: Promoting quality of life through collaborative practice. St. Louis, MO: Elsevier Pub.

MOBILE7932 : I think all of these models as explicated above cover the basis/background with regard to theoretical approaches that can be used to inform clinical decision-making to support clients. I think client-centred practice model should be mentioned as well.

MOBILE8741 : Goal setting should be updated, Doig & Fleming 2015 provide a "model" that agree with actual concepts in goal setting research. I will send you the book chapter. We are also working on an article about goal setting in line with these concepts.

More than the PEO model, I would advice to add a transactionalist model like Cutchin and Dickie 2013, so that the person-environment-occupation concept can better create a cylinder and blurr into each other than the PEO allows.

B. Simplify

MOBILE6146 : it is unclear how those theories are being applied at different stages

MOBILE8255 : I cannot help but think that the application of so many models dilutes the process? Is it possible to identify less that would be applicable.

C. Context

MOBILE6893 : If I was in setting where clients were provided support once their licence is cancelled, these models would be very useful. However, not as they exist in my State of Victoria. Theories are great if there is an infrastructure to support their implementation through local government or health system providers.

D. Other

MOBILE3940 : Anyone can come up with a model for procedure/ stages/ what is needed is a model, which can be applied and effect change positively and consistently

End of Round 3

You have answered the last question. You will be invited for the next round on February 15th. To validate your answers, press the submit button on this page.

Powered by

